

THE LEGAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE INITIATOR AND THE CROWDFUNDING PLATFORM OPERATOR

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The services provided by crowdfunding platforms are not significantly different from those offered by other platforms in the field of e-commerce. From the perspective of legal classification in platform relations, parallels can be drawn, particularly with auction platforms. Both serve as platforms that bring market participants together to conclude agreements according to a specific market mechanism established by the platform. Another similarity between the two is that any commission in favor of the platform is only charged if an agreement is successfully concluded within the market relations. Additionally, agreements within the market environment for a specific purpose can only be concluded within a pre-defined timeframe.

The relationship between the crowdfunding platform operator and its users is established through a service agreement. It is appropriate to distinguish between general and specific terms of use regarding crowdfunding platforms. Scholars such as Mollick (2014) and Belleflamme et al. (2013) emphasize the need to differentiate between general and specific agreements, as this approach facilitates the legal regulation of platform operations.

While the general agreement is a necessary condition for using the crowdfunding platform, the specific agreement pertains to conducting a particular crowdfunding round.

A) General Terms of Use Agreement

The general terms of use agreement between the initiator and the crowdfunding platform operator is a prerequisite for using the platform to conduct crowdfunding rounds. This contractual relationship typically regulates ongoing business interactions based solely on the platform's general terms of use. By registering on the platform, the initiator offers to enter into such an agreement ("click-to-accept"). Acceptance of this offer usually occurs after the participant completes the registration process, often via an automatically sent confirmation link delivered by email, which activates their account on the platform.

This agreement remains in effect for an indefinite period, lasting from the time the user registers on the platform until they are deregistered. Generally, the general terms of use agreement is established free of charge.

During the term of the agreement, there is a continuous exchange of recurring services, making it a matter of obligations that persist in the form of a framework agreement.

In cases where there is no obligation to conduct business, service relations should not exist as contractual relationships, even if they are provided free of charge. Instead, a sui generis (unique, non-standard) agreement, as specified in the platform's terms of use, should be adopted.

B) Specific Terms of Use Agreement

When an initiator activates a crowdfunding round, they submit a proposal to enter into a specific terms of use agreement with the crowdfunding platform, which differs from the general agreement. This proposal can be explicitly accepted by the crowdfunding platform, for example, through activation confirmation or upon the completion of technical processes, without requiring further input from the initiator.

The specific terms of use agreement is aimed at conducting a crowdfunding round. The typology of the agreement is determined by the nature of the service being provided, particularly whether it is a paid or unpaid agreement. Agrawal et al. (2014) highlight significant differences among platforms in this regard, as some operate on a commission basis, while others function on a donation-based model.

As a rule, crowdfunding platforms charge a commission only if the target amount is successfully raised. In such cases, a specific terms of use agreement is concluded in exchange for the fee. However, not all platforms charge a commission. Some platforms are financed exclusively through voluntary donations, and in such cases, the specific terms of use agreement is established free of charge.

The material content of the service is defined by the service elements provided by the crowdfunding platform, which are necessary to conduct a crowdfunding round. The primary factor is the availability of the platform's infrastructure to technically facilitate the crowdfunding round.

As part of the specific terms of use agreement, crowdfunding platforms undertake the obligation to provide their infrastructure. The purpose of the agreement is to ensure a system that enables market participants to establish contracts within the market environment. This includes creating a user profile,

transmitting information and explanations through the platform, and, most importantly, posting and presenting the relevant funding project to enable its accessibility to market participants.

By providing the platform infrastructure, crowdfunding platforms take on the responsibility of technically implementing the crowdfunding round. Scholars such as Agrawal et al. (2014) emphasize the legal complexities and risks associated with such processes for platforms, particularly in cases where a crowdfunding round fails.

If the specific terms of use agreement is established free of charge, the relationship represents a form of free business operation. The technical implementation of the crowdfunding round constitutes an operation carried out for the benefit of a third party.

If the specific terms of use agreement is fee-based, its legal classification is not immediately apparent and cannot be straightforwardly described as a commission-based agreement. The provision of platform infrastructure serves to conduct the crowdfunding round and, consequently, to facilitate the capitalization of the respective funding project. However, it is inappropriate to apply the regulations for intermediary contracts under the Civil Code to specific terms of use agreements.

Crowdfunding platforms, being integrated into crowdfunding rounds, should not typically engage in intermediary activities. They only offer the opportunity to establish business relationships through the provided platform infrastructure. This leads to significant parallels with auction platforms, where the application of intermediary contract regulations is also rejected.

The first argument against classifying the agreement as an intermediary contract is that the initiator does not have the right to enter into a contract with a specific sponsor (investor). According to the definition of an intermediary contract, under such an agreement, one party (the intermediary) undertakes, on behalf of the other party (the principal), to conclude one or more transactions with third parties in exchange for compensation, acting in their own name but at the principal's expense. Once the crowdfunding round is activated and a specific terms of use agreement is concluded, the initiator submits a legally significant declaration related to market relations. Upon the successful completion of the crowdfunding round, and ultimately through the fulfillment of technical procedures, contracts are established within the market relations framework. As a result, providing instructions, which is essential for the essence of an intermediary contract, becomes unnecessary for the initiator.

According to Chapter 48 of the Civil Code, a document confirming the possibility of entering into a contract is issued only if the crowdfunding platform allows the initiator to conduct "specific negotiations to conclude the primary contract they are seeking." In the crowdfunding market, no negotiations take place between project creators and investors regarding the details of the service. When the crowdfunding round begins, the characteristics of the service are already precisely defined by the project creator. The role of the crowdfunding platform is limited to creating an informational and technological infrastructure to facilitate the collection of funds. Here, the platform operator acts not as a direct intermediary between the initiator and the investors but as a service provider ensuring the conditions for fund collection.

In summary, crowdfunding platforms provide the infrastructure necessary to facilitate the financing process. Unlike intermediary activities, there are no direct agreements negotiated between investors and project creators. Applying the Civil Code's provisions on intermediary contracts to crowdfunding platforms is inappropriate since these platforms serve only as a technical tool linking projects with potential investors. Consequently, the crowdfunding process does not fit the definition of an intermediary contract, as platforms operate based on pre-established terms for project implementation, with no negotiations involved.

As mentioned, the crowdfunding process follows predefined technical procedures initiated with information provided by the project creator. In this sense, the process is managed entirely by the crowdfunding platform, leaving no room for independent actions. However, independent actions are essential for conducting business and are only possible if the initiator, as the business owner, retains a personal degree of responsibility, including decision-making authority. Furthermore, the crowdfunding platform does not purchase assets or influence the initiator's financial position. In the business context, the crowdfunding platform must act in the best interests of the project creator to safeguard against financial difficulties. Therefore, classifying the specific terms of use agreement as an agency agreement is inappropriate.

If independent activity is not present on the crowdfunding platform, the provisions of a service agreement may be applied. This implies that the platform's role is not that of an intermediary with independent obligations and responsibilities but rather that of a service provider.

A key characteristic of a service agreement is that the client is obligated to pay for the services provided within the terms and conditions specified in the

agreement. However, in the case of crowdfunding, the initiator is usually required to make the payment only if the crowdfunding round is successfully completed.

Unlike a service agreement, in a contract for work, the obligation to pay is based not on the completion of the work but on the successful outcome of that work. Therefore, the specific terms of use agreement in crowdfunding may fall under the provisions of a contract for work. The crowdfunding platform is responsible not for the success of the crowdfunding campaign but for its technical execution. The platform receives an agreed-upon commission only if the campaign is successful. If the campaign concludes unsuccessfully, the platform fully performs all technical aspects of the process but does not collect a commission. This does not exclude the application of contract-for-work provisions, as the agreed payment is contingent on achieving a specific result. In this case, the platform operates "at its own risk," and payment is made only upon the fulfillment of the specified condition—the success of the crowdfunding round. A contract to produce a work involves obligations tied to achieving a specific result, i.e., the successful completion of a particular task or work. However, since crowdfunding platforms primarily provide technical services, these relationships are typically governed by service agreements rather than contracts to produce a work.

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